

Teaching Artistic Gymnastics Techniques through Physical Education to Students in Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract:

This article describes the tasks of preschool education organizations to combine elements of rhythmic gymnastics in physical education classes in the form of dance, without the body, walking with objects, jumping, a series of exercises that require flexibility with music.

Keywords: Gymnastics, exercise, rhythmic gymnastics, walking, jumping, exercise, flexibility, music, physical qualities, body movements.

INTRODUCTION

Today, physical education and sports are becoming one of the priority areas of the world community. Among sports, gymnastics serves as the main tool in the process of physical education of children. To improve the quality of educational and educational activities in preschool education, to create advanced pedagogical, psychological and informational communication technologies and necessary conditions for the educational process within the framework of the broad political and social reforms that are being carried out in the life of our country. extensive work is being done. Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" defines the tasks of physical development of children in the process of preschool education and upbringing. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021", "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education system", President Shavkat In Mirziyoyev's Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, the tasks of forming physical feelings were set from the moment the child was born. This serves as a basis for the use of gymnastics in the physical education of children. Gymnastics is a means of physical education, along with games and sports tourism. Its main task is to provide

general physical training for various life activities. In addition, he can solve special tasks such as being able to hold his own body or control the movement of body parts, correcting physical defects in the body. Currently, the gymnastics system of the world's peoples is being critically studied, discarding the unnecessary, and scientifically embodying its beneficial aspects, it is being used positively in the conditions of physical education. All physical exercises can be used in gymnastics. In fact, it is used in the form of the following exercises.

a) line-up and re-line-up exercises: these exercises deal with rational ways of line-up, correct body posture, obeying commands, correcting height and stature, and other tasks;

b) basic physical exercises: these exercises are used for the development of all parts of the body in general or some isolated parts, they are convenient for the rapid formation of movement skills; Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". 23.09.2020 Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan. 29.12.2020.

c) free exercises: by this name we mean exercises composed in the form of a combination of movements performed under music. If we observe the movement of those engaged in free exercises, we will see that the movements fall into the rhythm and tempo of the music, or that it is elegant and beautiful, and you will realize that the reserve of human movements is very unique;

g) necessary life-practical exercises: there are walking, running, jumping, throwing, climbing, lifting and other exercises. These are the main tools in the development of physical qualities;

d) exercises performed in special gymnastic shells: exercises performed in perekladinadi, brusya, kon, yakkachop and others. They train strength, agility, joint mobility, muscle elasticity, mental and other qualities;

e) acrobatic exercises: handstands, turning sideways without bending the body, "randat", "flyag" and other exercises performed individually, in pairs, and in groups. They educate the basic, necessary, vital actions and skills. It is a leading tool for improving sports skills and general physical training;

f) rhythmic gymnastics: dance-style exercises performed without bodies, with bodies, includes a number of exercises that require walking, jumping, and flexibility, and it is understood to perform them with music, and it is a special type of sport.

It is necessary to use music that is simple in form and content, cheerful and invigorating in rhythmic gymnastics training. In this place, popular musical pieces, musical tunes encouraging dance and movement, waltzes, lively tunes, and modern popular songs are recommended. Before introducing musical tones into the training process, the teacher must be able to place the students appropriately. In addition, it is necessary to determine in advance the moment of inclusion of music in the process. While listening to music, each of us notices a pleasant beat that repeats itself in a rhythm, which in music is called a metric tone. Metric music divides music into bars. It is recommended to count while dancing, because any dance step consists of four movements. Each movement is done in eighths. You can record the exercise based on the beats or perform it by changing the position. Most of the movements included in rhythmic gymnastics are little different from the movements of classical and folk dances. However, rhythmic gymnastics has a number of its own elements, the technique of which is fundamentally different from the technique of choreographic exercises. Such elements should include spring-like movements, "wave"-like exercises, swings, some types of walking and running, and special jumps used in choreography. All these elements are widely used in free exercises. Spring-like movements are characterized by simultaneous bending of the body in several or all joints in the first phase of the movement, and simultaneous bending in the second phase. Bending and bending are done with tension. Spring-like movements with hands are

performed in various initial situations. The arms are flexed with tension in all joints (from the first phalanx of the fingers to the shoulder) in the direction relative to the body. The palm of the hand bends up and moves towards the shoulder, the elbow goes down and rests on the body. Handwriting occurs simultaneously with tension in all joints. The initial position - the arms are stretched out to the sides. The above actions are repeated again. Spring-like movements with the hands are defined by force and tension and are performed in different situations: hands in front, at the sides, above and below. It is necessary to bend the hands exactly in the direction of the initial position, without twisting the wrists and paws. Bending in all joints should be performed with tension, as if overcoming resistance. In this case, the head is slightly bent forward. The movement of writing in all joints is performed with strength, slightly raising the head. Spring-like movements with the legs. It is performed while standing on half toes by keeping the tips of both feet and knees together. Lowering the legs from the half toes to the heels, one should sit in such a way that the pelvis should be located on the heels. Returning to the original position by writing the legs. Spring-like movements can be performed in a sitting and semi-sitting position in different rhythms. In short, regular gymnastics improves blood circulation in the tissues, lowers arterial pressure, improves the functioning of the cardiovascular system, increases the respiratory capacity of the lungs, improves metabolism, and improves the central nervous system. and has a positive effect on the mental state of the neuromuscular apparatus, increases its vitality, self-confidence, and inspires. The system of gymnastic exercises is constantly developing and growing. Scientific research and observations show that some exercises are being restructured, updated, and some are being strengthened and improved.

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